

Short communication

First record of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) for Austria

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Abstract. The first record of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) for Austria is reported. Additional information on the finding is given. The European distribution of the species is summarised.

Key words: Heteroptera, *Zelus renardii*, distribution, new record, invasive species, Graz, Austria.

The leafhopper assassin bug *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) is an invasive Nearctic species which has colonised various European countries and is mainly distributed in the Mediterranean Region. Recently, Kment & van der Heyden (2022) provided a list and a map of the known distribution of the species on the European continent and adjacent islands. Furthermore, Lukashuk et al. (2022) reported the first registration of *Z. renardii* in Belarus, most likely an accidental introduction, van der Heyden (2022) published a paper on the first record of the species in Bulgaria, and John & Kolokotronis (2023) reported the first record of the species for Cyprus.

Herein, the first record of *Z. renardii* from Austria is reported.

Material examined: AUSTRIA: Graz, Lat.: 47.126269, Long.: 15.4366, 27.IV.2023, 1 ex., phot. V. Staudinger.

On 27.IV.2023, the second author found and photographed an adult specimen of *Z. renardii* in the Austrian city of Graz (Fig. 1). The specimen was found when it crawled out of a broccoli which had been added to the compost in the garden of the second author's family.

The nearest records of *Z. renardii* reported are from Southwest Germany (van der Heyden 2021a), Croatia, the Czech Republic and Northern Italy (see Kment & van der Heyden 2022).

In some other cases of findings of *Z. renardii* in European regions north of the Mediterranean Region, the specimens were introduced accidentally – imported with fruits, e.g. from Italy and Greece (van der Heyden 2021b).

Very likely, the specimen of *Z. renardii* reported in this note was not introduced accidentally from the Mediterranean Region: the broccoli had been bought from an organic farm in St Nikolai im Sausal, located south of Graz, and had been stored in a plastic bag in a refrigerator before it was added to the compost. No organic waste of imported fruits or vegetables was added to the compost within several weeks.

As *Z. renardii* has not been reported from Austria in scientific publications yet, this is the country's first species record.

Fig. 1. Specimen of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857, Graz, Austria (photo: Valerian Staudinger).

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